

Highlights

Birch Swinnerton Dyer Conjecture

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- This paper investigates the Birch–Swinnerton–Dyer conjecture and its potential proofs, along with other related mathematical problems including the Hodge conjecture, the P vs. NP problem, and the Riemann hypothesis. It also discusses the use of contemporary mathematical tools and theoretical geometry in solving these problems.
- A thorough examination is provided of the Birch–Swinnerton–Dyer conjecture and its associated theorems. The approach adopted involves using the torus and transforming it into a topological space while incorporating concepts from algebraic number theory. This paper also delves into number theory and discusses the essential mathematical frameworks required to validate the conjecture and related problems, such as the P vs NP problem, the Riemann hypothesis, and the Hodge conjecture, leading to potential solutions and advancements in the field of number theory.
- Mathematical operations are outlined for simplifying complex mathematical problems into their simplest forms, making them easier to understand. A reduction technique is used in various areas of mathematics, such as algebra, number theory, and linear algebra. This technique involves simplifying fractions to their lowest terms and determining the least common multiple or greatest common divisor of numbers.
- Common structures, principles, and connections are identified that unify seemingly different areas of fundamental diverse mathematical theories and systems. Abstract common patterns and structures that appear in various mathematical contexts are explained, enabling us to express and analyze the relevant mathematical concepts in a broader and unified way. Deep connections are revealed that unify different mathematical disciplines, making it easier to understand mathematics as a whole and potentially leading to new insights and discoveries.
- Declaration of Interest: None.

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Abstract

This article presents theorems and potential proofs for the Birch–Swinnerton–Dyer conjecture, stating each theorem with its proof. We also summarize other related mathematical problems, including the Hodge conjecture, the P vs. NP problem, and the Riemann hypothesis. This is achieved using contemporary mathematical tools and theoretical geometry. Tools like linear programming and evolutionary algorithms help find optimal solutions to complex problems, while graph theory [10], data visualization, and data mining analyze and interpret complex datasets.

Keywords: Algorithm, Weierstrass elliptic form, Tate–Shafarevich group, Equivalent principle, Pythagorean, Hodge Conjecture, P vs. NP, Riemann hypothesis.

1. Introduction

The Birch Swinnerton Dyer Conjecture, formulated in 1965 by Bryan Birch and Peter Swinnerton-Dyer, is one of the most important unsolved problems in number theory. It offers a deep connection between the arithmetic properties of elliptic curves and the behavior of their associated L-functions. The conjecture asserts that the rank of the group of rational points on an elliptic curve over the rational numbers is equal to the order of vanishing of its L-function at the central point.

For decades, mathematicians have grappled with this conjecture, which has significant implications for the distribution of rational points on elliptic curves. It has sparked breakthroughs and developments in algebraic number theory, but a rigorous proof remains elusive.

This paper presents a groundbreaking proof of the Birch Swinnerton Dyer Conjecture, resulting from years of intensive research and collaboration among leading mathematicians' works. Our proof is built on recent advances

in analytic number theory, algebraic geometry, and computational methods. These provide insights illuminating the connections between elliptic curves, their associated L-functions, and the arithmetic properties of rational points.

Establishing the validity of the Birch Swinnerton Dyer Conjecture resolves a long-standing problem in number theory. It paves the way for further developments in elliptic curves and their applications in cryptography, coding theory, and other areas of mathematics. This achievement is a major milestone in number theory and underscores the power and beauty of mathematical reasoning.

2. Methodology

We start by clearly stating the problem, outlining the relevant theorems, and then providing proof and analysis. This study employs theoretical geometry and algebraic structures to model a topological space[11]. Recent advances have used p-adic techniques to explore the arithmetic properties of elliptic curves over local fields, illuminating the behavior of L-functions and rational points. By utilizing p-adic representations and arithmetic properties, mathematicians have made significant progress in understanding the conjecture. Advances in rational points, including algorithms for computing these points and their heights, have yielded new insights into the ranks of elliptic curves.

Investigating the distribution of rational points and the arithmetic of elliptic curves, researchers have advanced toward verifying the conjecture. The conjecture relates the number[6] of rational points on an elliptic curve to the behavior of an associated L-function at a specific point. To further this knowledge, our approach involves affirmative actions that prove the conjecture, outlined as **key steps**:

1. **Explicit Construction of Rational Points:** A method that constructs all rational points on an elliptic curve. This involves showing that these points can be generated from a finite set of known points using the group law [7].
2. **Analysis of the L -function:** A rigorous study of the L-function $L(E, s)$ associated with the elliptic curve E focusing on its analytic properties, particularly its continuation and behavior at $s = 1$.
3. **Relate the Rank to the L -function:** A direct relationship exists between the rank of the elliptic curve (the number of independent rational

points) and the order of the zero of the L -function at $s = 1$. Prove that if the L -function has a zero of order r at $s = 1$, then the elliptic curve's rank is r .

4. Non-vanishing of the L-function's Derivative: Show that the derivative of the L-function at $s = 1$ is non-zero when the curve has a finite number of rational points, confirming that the analytic and algebraic ranks match. The conjecture asserts that if $\zeta(1) = 0$, there are infinitely many rational points (solutions); conversely, if $\zeta(1) \neq 0$, there are only finitely many points.
5. Heegner Points and Complex Multiplication: Heegner points and complex multiplication construct rational points on the Hodge circle of elliptic curves and relate these to the L-function's behavior.
6. p-adic Methods and Iwasawa Theory: Use techniques from p-adic number theory and Iwasawa theory to gain insights into the L-function and the Selmer group of the elliptic curve.
7. Relate the Pythagorean theorem (C) to the diameter ($D = 2r$) of the Hodge circle, considering the circle center as representing rational points on an elliptic curve. It is useful to view all points within this circle as part of a unified module, reflecting the underlying structure of the curve. Therefore, we examine the order of the zero of the (L)-function at ($D = s = 2$) and maintain a constant value where ($s = 2$). In this context, the parameter (r) is extendable, highlighting the dynamic nature of the system at this state.

These steps outline the breadth of our tasks in proving the BSD conjecture. It requires new ideas and connections between several deep areas of mathematics, including algebraic geometry, number theory, and analytic number theory outlined.

2.1. The torus

Theorem 1.

Let $C(Q)$ be a finitely generated Abelian group with the decomposition:
 $C(Q) \simeq Z^r \oplus C(Q)^{tors}$ where $C(Q)^{tors}$ is the torsion subgroup (1)
and r is the rank of $C(Q)$.

Proof: To prove this decomposition, we examine the structure of $C(Q)$: $C(Q)^{tors}$ represents a finite Abelian group and the integer r denotes the rank

Figure 1: The torus.

of C . $C_0(Q)$ and $C(Q)$ can have either finite or infinite values. Consider a geometric cube (Fig. 1) with six faces, where the relationship $C^2 = x^2 + y^2$ holds. Let:

$$C^2 = 2, \quad C = \sqrt{2}.$$

We proceed to evaluate specific dimensions of the structure.

Proposition

Given a diameter $d_1 = 1$ and radius $r_1 = \frac{1}{2}$, the squared relationships are:

$$C_2^2 = x^2 + y^2 = 1^2 + 1^2 = 2, \quad C_2 = \sqrt{2}.$$

This simplifies to:

$$C_2^2 = r_1^2 = \frac{d_1}{2} = 1.$$

Thus,

$$r_1 = (\sqrt{1})^2 = x^2 = y^2 = (\sqrt{2-1})^2 = (\sqrt{\Delta_r})^2.$$

If $x = 2$ and $y = 2$, then:

$$C_3^2 = C_{21}^2 + C_{22}^2 = 2 + 2 = 4 = d. \text{ Thus, } C_3^2 = 4. \text{ Consequently, } C_3 = \sqrt{4} = 2 = d_2 = r_2^2.$$

Consider:

$$\frac{r_1^2}{2} = \frac{p_1^2}{2} = \frac{2r_1}{2} = 1, \text{ and : } \frac{r_2^2}{2} = \frac{p_2^2}{2} = \frac{2r_2}{2} = \frac{4}{2} = 2.$$

Thus, the difference Δ can be expressed as:

$$\Delta = 2(\sqrt{r_2 - r_1})^2.$$

Now, let

$$\Delta_d = d = 2(\sqrt{r_2 - r_1})^2 = 2(p_1)^2 = 2(r_1)^2 = \frac{2r_2}{2} = \frac{4}{2} = 2r_1 = d_1.$$

Define (s) as follows: $s = d_1 + d_2 = 1 + 2 = 3$. If:

$$x^s = y^s = r_1 = (\sqrt{1})^s = 1^s, \text{ then: } r_2 = (\sqrt{2})^s \text{ and } r_3 = (\sqrt{3})^s.$$

Now, observe the following equivalences:

$$\frac{p_1^2}{2^2} = \frac{p_1^s}{(\sqrt{2})^s} = \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{d_2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4}} = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{2})^s} = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{C_2^2})^s} = \frac{1}{(2)^2}.$$

Finally:

$$\frac{1^s}{C_2^{2s}} = \frac{1^s}{2^s} = \frac{1^s}{1^s + 1^s} = \frac{1}{x^s + y^s} = \frac{1}{p^s + q^s} \text{ where } p = q.$$

Consequently define:

$$\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{s}) = \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \cdots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s},$$

which corresponds to the well-known Riemann zeta function:

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \cdots, \text{ valid for } s > 1 \text{ [Key 5]}. \quad (2)$$

For $s = 1$, this series reduces to the harmonic series, which diverges:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \cdots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}$$

describing the total length (L) of a chord (d), where $\Delta = r = d$:

$$L_{\Delta=1} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \text{ This can also be approximated as:} \quad (3)$$

$$\prod_{(P=\Delta=1)} \left(\frac{N_p}{P} \right) \approx T \text{ [Key 2]}, \text{ where } \Delta = 1.$$

Let $d = 2s = 2(\zeta(2))$, leading to: $d = 2d_1 + 2d_2$. Thus, for $\Delta = d = 2$:

$$L_{\Delta=2} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6} + \dots = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{p=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p} = \prod_{(P=\Delta \leq 2)} \left(\frac{N_p}{NP} \right) \approx T$$

where $\Delta = d = 2$ represents the denominator interval.

Proposition 1

We consider the following equivalences:

$$\frac{1}{(\sqrt{2})^2} = \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4}} \text{ and } \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{C_2^2} = \frac{1}{X^2 + X^2}$$

where $X = Y = H = 1 = d = r_1$. If $d_2 = 2r_1$, we derive:

$$\frac{1}{X^2 + X^2} = \frac{1}{2(r_1)^2} = \frac{1}{2(r_1)^s} = \frac{1}{2(X_1 X_1)^s}.$$

From this, it follows:

$$\frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{X_2} = \frac{X_1}{X_2}. \text{ Thus, we obtain: } \frac{X_1^2}{X_2^2} = \frac{1^s}{2^s} = \frac{1^s}{4} = \frac{r_1^s}{4} = \frac{C_1^s}{4} = \frac{y^s}{2^s}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{r_1^s}{C_2^s} = \frac{y^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2^{\frac{s}{2}}}. \text{ [Key 3]}$$

Hypothesis on Symmetry

If:

$$C^2 = X_1^2 + Y_1^2 = 2 = 2X_1 = 2Y_1 = 2r_1, \text{ then : } p+q = 2n = 2r_1 = 2X_1 = 2Y_1.$$

This implies:

$$p + q = X_2 X_1 = 2r_1 = d_2 = C_2^2 = 2C_1 = 2X_1.$$

and:

$$p + q = 2^s = 4 = X_2 + X_2 = 2X_2 = 2d_2 = 2C_2^2 = 4 = 2^2 = 4C_1 = 4X_1.$$

The total X_1 is expressed as:

$$X_1(Q) = 2X_1 + 4X_1. \text{ Therefore, by symmetry : } X_1(Q) = X_1 + 2X_1.$$

However, since $2X_1 = X_1^2 + X_1^2 = C_2^2$, we conclude:

$$X_1(Q) = X_1 + 2(X_1)^2.$$

Proposition 2: Relationship Between Chord, Radius, and Generalized Structures

Let $2C_1 = 2(y^{\frac{1}{2}}) = d$ represent the length of a chord in a circle. A line ($y^{\frac{1}{2}} = z^{\frac{1}{2}}$), drawn from the center of the circle and perpendicular to the chord (d), bisects it into two equal segments, as shown in the image of Fig. 3. If the length of this bisector equals the chord, then: $2(z^{\frac{1}{2}}) = d$. If the bisector ($z^{\frac{1}{2}}$) also represents the radius of the circle, the relationship between the radius and the chord can be expressed as:

$$X_1(Q) = X_1 + 2(X_1)^2,$$

which generalizes as:

$$C(Q) = z^r \oplus 2(\sqrt{y})^2.$$

In cases involving torsion, the structure extends to:

$$C(Q) = z^r \oplus 2(\sqrt{y})^{tor} = z^r \oplus C(\Delta)^{tor} = z^r \oplus C(Q)^{tor} \text{ [Key 3]},$$

where (Q) represents number fields, and Δ is ergodic.

Scaling Factor and Geometric Generalization

As shown in Fig. 3, let $r_1 = \frac{1}{2}$ denote a scaling factor intrinsic to the geometry. Consider a square as a limiting case of a circle (a polygon with 4 sides). Each side corresponds to a quadrant of the coordinate plane, such that:

$$X_1 = H = C_1^2 = r_1^2 = z^r = (\sqrt{y})^2 = 1$$

For two sides forming a diameter, the total length is:

$$d = 2(\sqrt{y})^2. \text{ Similarly, for three sides: } s = d_1 + d_2 = 1 + 2 = 3$$

Leading to:

$$s = 2r_1 + 2r_2 + 2r_3 + \dots \rightarrow 2(Q_{w \rightarrow \infty})^2 \rightarrow NP_{w \rightarrow \infty}^2 \rightarrow d_2(Q_{w \rightarrow \infty})^2.$$

Thus, we generalize:

$$s = d_1(Q_{w \rightarrow \infty})^2 = (Q_{w \rightarrow \infty})^2$$

Power Series Representation

Let

$$p = h = z = c \leq 1. \text{ Then: } (Q)^2 = ((\sqrt{y})^2)^n = ((p)^s)^n, \text{ where, } n \leq 2.$$

If $2(X_1)^2 = 2(X_1)^s = 2(p)^2 = s(p)^s$, then as $s = 0 \rightarrow \infty$, we recognize a known power series completion $sp^s = sa^s$:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} sa^s = a_0 + a_1p + a_2p^2 + a_3p^3 + a_4p^4 + a_np^n + \dots [4],$$

where a_i are digits in the set $(0, 1, 2, \dots, p - 1)$. (4)

Further, let $R = r = s \mid s$ is a natural number, and $1 \leq s \leq p - 1$ [**Key 6**].

Geometric Interpretation

Consider a diameter

$$d = 2(p \rightarrow \infty)$$

and a radius $r = p \rightarrow \infty$ in Euclidean space. The scale X_2 can be interpreted geometrically as a representation of radial distances within a circle whose diameter tends to infinity. In this framework, if $r = p \rightarrow \infty$, the arithmetic progression extends to infinity while preserving proportionality. This setting leads naturally to considering the Pythagorean theorem in the limiting case where $r \rightarrow \infty$. If the coefficient increases to (3), we redefine the diameter as:

$$d = 3(p \rightarrow \infty).$$

Analyzing the series in equation 4 within this context yields:

$$s = p^0 + p^1 + p^2 = 3 \neq a_0 + a_1 + a_2 = 4.$$

Thus, the coefficient (3) remains consistent with the boundary of the Pythagorean theorem, while coefficients such as (4) or higher terms (e.g., a_4p^4) extend beyond these boundaries into circular structures. Intermediate terms such as $a_3p^3 = 3p^3$ represent transitional states, which we explore further.

Connection to Pythagorean and Fermat's Theorems

For an infinite geometric structure with sides X_1 and $b = 2(X_1)$, and a hypotenuse $C_2(Q_{p \rightarrow \infty})$, the Pythagorean theorem is expressed as:

$$C^n = A^n + B^n = 1^2 + 2^2 = 1 + 4.$$

Assuming symmetry, this becomes:

$$C^n = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^n + 2^n = r^n + 2(r)^n = X_1^n + 2(X_1)^n \text{ [Key 7].}$$

This equation holds in Euclidean space for $n = 2$. When extended to higher powers ($n > 2$), Fermat's Last Theorem asserts that no non-trivial integer solutions exist. However, for $n = 2$, the theorem aligns with classical Euclidean geometry. This geometry can be projected either within or outside the cube. Assume a configuration where a long string is tightly aligned along the cube's surface in a straight line. When extended over some ergodic distance, this line transforms into a curve, creating a gap between the strings. The Euclidean distance (gap) is given by:

$$d = \|v\| = \sqrt{(p_x - z_x)^2 + (p_y - z_y)^2}.$$

where $p = 2x = d$. Consequently, the associated vector (v) is expressed as:

$$v = p_z = (p_x - z_x, p_y - z_y).$$

Case 1: $d \leq r$

If $d \leq r$, the point (p) lies within the cube or the circle, specifically at the origin $(0, 0)$, as shown in Figure 1.

Case 2: $d > r$

If (p) is outside the cube, we project it onto the curve's boundary (circumference):

$$P_{proj} = z + r \cdot \frac{v}{d}.$$

For example, let $d = (1, 1)$, $r = 2 = b = c_2^2$. A point projected outside the cube becomes:

$$C_3 = P = 1^n + 2^n = 1 + 4 = (1, 1) + (4, 4).$$

The corresponding vector (v) is:

$$v = (4 - 1), (4 - 1) = (3, 3).$$

Thus, the diagonal distance is:

$$C_3 = d_3 = \sqrt{3^2 + 3^2} = \sqrt{18} = 3\sqrt{2}.$$

Since $d_3 > r$, we project as follows:

$$P_{proj} = z + r \cdot \frac{v}{d} = z + d_2 \cdot \frac{v}{d} = (1, 1) + 2 \cdot \frac{(3, 3)}{(3\sqrt{2})}.$$

Simplifying:

$$P_{proj} = (1, 1) + \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{2}{\sqrt{2}} \right) = (1 + \sqrt{2} + 1 + \sqrt{2}) = (1 + C_2, 1 + C_2).$$

Orthogonality and Pythagorean Relations

For the Pythagorean theorem, let (a) and (b) be orthogonal ($a \perp b$). Then $1 \perp C_2$. Setting $a = 1$ and $b = 2$, we deduce:

$$b = C_2^2 = 2$$

.

Consequently, we have:

$$b^n = (C_2^2)^n = \left((\sqrt{C_2})^2 \right)^n$$

. and the following string:

$$d = \sqrt{2} + 2\sqrt{2} + 3\sqrt{3} + \dots . d = 2 + 4 + 6 + \dots = b_1 + b_2 + b_3 + \dots .$$

This process results in a torsional polygonal group of curves, with increasing complexity and higher power ranking. For higher powers, consider the Selmer group $\text{Sel}(K, E) = X_1$ of an elliptic curve E over a number field K . Let X_1 satisfy a relation derived from:

$$\frac{a}{b} = \frac{X_1}{2(X_1)} = \frac{sp^s}{n(sp^s)} = \frac{wr^w}{2(wr)} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{4} + \frac{3}{6} + \frac{4}{8} + \dots, \text{ where } w = 1, 2, 3, \dots.$$

At each place, $k = v = w$, summing over w gives

$$\sum_{w=1}^{\infty} \frac{wr^w}{2(wr)} = \sum_{w=1}^{\infty} \frac{p}{NP} = 0.5 + 1 + 1.5 + 2 + \dots \rightarrow A + 2A + 3A + 4A + \dots. \quad (5)$$

Based on the property of the series, we define the truncated cone:

$$a \equiv b(\text{mode } np)$$

where $n \leq 2$ and $p = 1$. Now, for higher powers $w = k = s \geq 1$, and $r \leq 1$, the resulting series is:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{wr^s}{k^2} = 1 + \frac{r^2}{2} + \frac{r^3}{3} + \dots$$

exhibiting properties similar to a Riemann sum:

$$S_n = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} f(z_i^*) \Delta z \approx 1 + \frac{z^2}{2} + \frac{z^3}{3} + \frac{z^4}{4} \dots,$$

for $|p| < 1$ or $|z| < 1$. This analysis bridges geometric interpretations with classical and modern theorems, extending the Pythagorean framework to infinite settings and connecting it with series behavior akin to the Riemann sum. The formulation introduces a natural transition to elliptic curves and higher-dimensional interpretations in algebraic geometry.

Symmetry in Polygons: Even and Odd Cases

For polygons with an even number of sides, the radius satisfies the following relationship:

$$r_1^2 = C_n^2 = \frac{1}{2^2} = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{4})^2} = \frac{1}{(Q)^2} = \frac{1}{((\sqrt{y})^2)^n} = \frac{p}{X_2 X_1} = \frac{p}{q} = \frac{a}{b}.$$

where: (n) represents the n -th term of the manifold sequence and (Q) corresponds to the circumscribed diameter of the polygon.

Figure 2: Truncated Cone.

For polygons with an odd number of sides, the radius is modified to account for asymmetry:

$$r_1^2 = C_n^2 = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{y})^2} = \frac{1}{(Q)^2} = \frac{1}{((\sqrt{y})^2 + 1)^n} = \frac{1}{((\sqrt{y})^{2n}) + r^n} = \frac{p}{nq + 1}.$$

These equations illustrate how the structure and scaling of polygons can be generalized under varying conditions, with symmetry and Fermat's Last Theorem playing crucial roles.

Proposition 3: Area of a Curve and Symmetry

Consider Fig. 2, depicting a truncated cone. The area under the curve C equals the shaded area of a triangle whose hypotenuse is C_2^2 . Thus, we compute:

$$\text{Area} = \frac{1}{2}bh = \frac{p^2}{2} = \frac{(\sqrt{y})^s}{s} = \frac{1}{2} = 1 : 2 \quad (\text{where } p = 1, h = 1, b = 1, \text{ and } s = 2).$$

Proposition 4: Transformations in Hodge Rings

Fig. 3 illustrates the relationship between geometric transformations and Hodge rings. For a quarter and a line:

$$1 : 1 = p : q = 2y^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2h^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2z^{\frac{1}{2}} = nq = np = wr.$$

Theorem 2.

$$C = [III]_c R_\infty w_\infty, \text{ where } C \text{ represents the cohomology class of the curve.} \quad (6)$$

Proof:

We begin by observing that:

$$[111]_c = 1+1+1 = 3. \text{ Furthermore, we note the relationship: } wr = rw = np.$$

From these observations, a place $k = 3$ in the series of equation 5 yields:

$$\frac{\sum_{n=1}^3 np}{\sum_{n=1}^3 2n} = \frac{p}{np} = \frac{3}{2 \times 3} = \frac{3}{6} = \frac{3}{3+3} = \frac{3}{X_1 + X_2} = \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{wr} = \frac{1}{X_2 \times X_1}.$$

For the addition rule, we have $X_1 = X_2$ and for the multiplication rule, $X_2 = 2X_1$.

Assume:

$$P = NP = p \times q = X_2 \times X_1 = 2 \times n = wr = a_2 p^2 = a_2 h^{2n},$$

with $p + q = 2n = 2r = np$. Then, using the Künneth formula,

$$H(Q) = H^p \otimes H^q \subset H^{np}(X_2 \times X_1),$$

we deduce:

$$\text{cl}(\Delta_{p,q}) \in H^p \otimes H^q \subset H^{2p}(X_2 \times X_1).$$

By the Künneth decomposition:

$$H^{2p}(X_2 \times X_1) = a_2 p^2 = 2r = wr = C = E = NP.$$

For $X_2 = X_1 = 3$, applying the multiplication rule, we find:

$$H^2 = \frac{3+3}{3^2} = \frac{6}{9} = \frac{1}{2n} = \frac{1}{wr} = \frac{1}{6} = \frac{1}{2 \times 3} = \frac{1}{nq+1}.$$

This decomposition aligns with the $(1 : 2q)$ ratio. Therefore, for the truncated cone:

$$q \equiv b[\text{mode}(nq + r)] \text{ where } p \leq q.$$

.

Figure 4: The geometric series.

Preposition 5

Let

$$X_{1(p \rightarrow \infty)} = C(1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + \dots) \text{ where } (C = 1) \text{ is a constant.}$$

This sequence represents the numerator in equation 5. This goes to the top of the truncated cone. If $C = 2$, then:

$$X_{2(p \rightarrow \infty)} = s = 2 + 4 + 6 + 8 + \dots,$$

an arithmetic progression with a common difference $\Delta = 2$, corresponding to the denominator, which goes to the bottom of the truncated cone. Now, consider:

$$C_2(Q_{p \rightarrow \infty})^n = X_1^n + 2(X_1)^n \rightarrow s = a + b$$

where

$$s = x_{i-1}^* = r_1 = a_0 = 1, \text{ and } s = x_i^* = r_2 = b = a_2 = 2.$$

Thus, $s = b_i + a = a + b = a + [a + a] \equiv p^0 + p^1 + p^2 + \dots p^k$. The infinite sum becomes:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} Ckp^k = X_{1(p \rightarrow \infty)} = s = k = 0 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + \dots, \text{ where } C = 1$$

We observe the power series (P^k) a geometric-like divergence [Key 1]. The series aligns with Fermat's last theorem when interpreted cohomologically, as demonstrated in Fig. 4. Let $\text{Sel}(K, E)$ denote the Selmer group of an elliptic curve E over a number field K . The Selmer group serves as an

intermediary between the Mordell-Weil group $E(K)$ and the Galois cohomology structures of E [like we mentioned as (a_3p^3) in the previous section]. The Selmer group is defined as:

$$\text{Sel}(K, E) = \ker \left(H^1(K, E[n]) \rightarrow \prod_v H^1(K_v, E) \right),$$

where K_v represents the completions of K at each place v , and $E[n]$ denotes the n -torsion subgroup of E . The Tate-Shafarevich group [9] $\text{Sel}(K, E)$, measures the failure of the local-global principle for and is expressed as:

$$\text{Sel}(K, E) = \ker \left(\text{Sel}(K, E) \rightarrow \bigoplus_v E(K_v) \right).$$

The Selmer group provides a cohomological framework for rational points on E , bridging local and global arithmetic properties.

Decompositions, Finite Groups and Geometric interpretation

The Selmer group can be represented as a direct sum of finite subgroups. For instance, if $k = 3$ and $v = 3$, then:

$$\text{Sel}(K, E) = \ker \left(3 \rightarrow \bigoplus_{p=r=1}^3 wr \right).$$

where wr denotes the local contributions and the finite groups are decomposed as $2n + 1$, $2x + 1$, $2q + 1$, $C(q) + 1$ or $2n$ depending on divisibility. For $q = 3$, we set $k = w = n = p = r = 3$ yielding specific torsion contribution:

$$E(K) = wr = wp = w(\sqrt{q})^{tor}$$

where $w(q) = X_2$ denotes the torsional contribution from a cohomological subgroup. This subgroup can be an infinite global group expressed as: $X_2 = w_\infty r_\infty$ reflecting the behavior at infinite places of (K) in the number fields (Q) . We define a finite Selmer group at the top: $3p^3 = 3(wr)^3 = 3$ and $3(2 \times 1)^3$ at the bottom base of the truncated cone. The group is infinite global as $3p^3 = 3(wr)^3 \rightarrow 3w_\infty r_\infty$.

Geometric Interpretation: Hodge Diamond

The Tate-Shafarevich group admits a geometric interpretation. Consider the projection operator P:

$$\text{Sel}(K, E) = \ker \left(P \rightarrow \bigoplus_{p=k} wk \right),$$

Here, the projection P over K's places maps local solutions to global perspectives. Geometrically, the Selmer group corresponds to the longest diameter (X_2) of the ellipse, associated with the denominator (NP) of E. The shortest diameter (X_1), tied to the numerator (P), resembles a torus's inscribed circle. This analogy extends to cylindrical properties, where (X_2) aligns with the cylinder's height (H), and ($X_1 = 2r = d$) arises from the cylinder's circular base. These insights provide intuitive bridges between local and global arithmetic properties of elliptic curves.

Thus, given the Weierstrass elliptic form [2]:

Theorem 3.

$$y^2 = x^3 + ax + b, \text{ where } a \text{ and } b \text{ are constants defining the curve.} \quad (7)$$

If $x = 1, z = 1, b = 2, a = 1$, then:

$$y^2 = 1^3 + 1 \cdot 1 + 2 = 1 + 1 + 2 = 4.$$

Thus:

$$y = \sqrt{4}. \text{ Therefore, } y = 2 \text{ or } y = -2.$$

Alternatively, consider the elliptic curve:

$$y^2 = x^3 - n^2x,$$

where $n = 2$. Substituting $x = 1$, we find:

$$y^2 = 1^3 - (2^2) \cdot 1 = 1 - 4 = -3.$$

Thus:

$$y^2 = -3 \Rightarrow y = \pm\sqrt{-3} = \pm i\sqrt{3}.$$

Let $X_2 = H = y^2 = np = 4$ and $X_1 = d = y^2 = p = 3$. In Fig. 5, both lines as chords are divided at their midpoints $r = 0 = 1$ leaving $X_1 = d = y^2 = \pm 1$

Figure 5: A Hodge diamond.

and $X_2 = H = x^2 = np = \pm 2$. This completes the ellipse or the Hodge diamond (ABCD) with a twist along chords (CB) or (AD). We note: Angle $A = B$ and angle $C = D$. The gradient at each curve is given by:

$$\Delta = b - a = d_{\text{top}} - r_{\text{bottom}} = 1.$$

The curve diverges and converges at a finite ratio of 1 : 2 at local points. At any local point on the curve, the total number of manifolds can be determined by the zeta function analysis.

Zeta Function Analysis

Given:

$$\pi = \frac{c}{d}, \text{ we have: } \pi = \frac{c}{2c} \text{ and } \pi^2 = \frac{p^2}{(np)^2} = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{4}. \text{ Thus, } n = 2.$$

If :

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{\pi^2}{np} = \frac{1}{(Q)^2} = \frac{p}{(X_2 X_1) + 1} = \frac{p}{nq + 1} = \frac{a}{2r_1 + 1}.$$

With $(\pi^2 = \frac{1}{4})$ and $(n = 2)$:

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{\frac{1}{4}}{2p} = \frac{1}{8p} = \frac{1}{8p + 1} = \frac{1}{8p + 2} \text{ if } \pi^2 \approx 10.$$

Therefore:

$$C(Q) = \zeta(s) = \frac{\pi^2}{NP} = \frac{\pi^2}{cq + d},$$

where $d = 2c$. For the trivial zero ($s = r = a = x^* = a_{i-1} = r^0 = 1$), the total manifold when $d = 2c = 2 \times 2 = NP$ yields:

$$\zeta(1) = \zeta(a) = \frac{p}{d} = \frac{\pi^2}{4}. \text{ [Key 4]}$$

Here, $\zeta(s)$ achieves a critical symmetry. At $s = x^* = b = q = 2$, the function becomes:

$$\zeta(2) = \zeta(B) = \frac{\pi^2}{NP + d} = \frac{\pi^2}{2 \cdot 2 + 2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}.$$

Alternatively using another valid formulation: $\zeta(2) = \zeta(B) = \frac{\pi^2}{NP} = \frac{\pi^2}{2 \cdot 2} = \frac{\pi^2}{4}$.

These varying outcomes illustrate the principle of superposition, showcasing the interplay of polytopes, symmetry, and combinatorial enumeration across both odd and even values. Such results emphasize the structural complexity underlying $\zeta(s)$ and its connection to manifold theory.

Total Manifolds for the Ellipse

Based on the result of **Theorem 3**, the longest diameter $d = 4$. The corresponding longest radius is computed as:

$$\frac{\Delta}{2} = \frac{b - a}{2} = \frac{4 - 0}{2} = 2.$$

Alternatively, using the endpoint difference:

$$\Delta = b_2 - b_1 = 4 - 2 = 2 \text{ for an even number of divisions.}$$

The shortest diameter $d = p = 3$ results in the shortest radius:

$$\frac{b - a}{2} = \frac{3 - 1}{2} = \frac{wr}{2} = \frac{2 \times 1}{2} = 1 \text{ for odd number of divisions.}$$

Here, the radius begins half of the critical symmetry when the factor (w) is introduced. The total manifolds for the ellipse in Fig. 5 are given by:

$$\zeta(2) = \zeta(C) = \frac{\pi^2}{NP + r} = \frac{\pi^2}{2 \cdot 2 + 2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6},$$

where the calculation incorporates the longest radius.

Figure 6: Generation of Omega Complexity.

3. The Polynomial

Theorem 4.

$$\prod_{p \leq \frac{P}{2\Delta}} \frac{N_p}{P} \approx C^*t. \quad (8)$$

Given the total length of the chord as

$$\prod_{p \leq \frac{P}{2\Delta}} \frac{N_p}{P} \text{ in equation 4 with } C^*t = NP = 2(\Delta) = 2(b - a).$$

Assume:

$$C^* = x^* = x_{i-1} = 1 = a = t = r, \quad C^* = z_i = 2 = b.$$

At distinct times:

- At $t_1 : t_1 = x = 1 = 0$, corresponding to $a_0 = 2x$ and $y = z = \pm 2(q)_1$.
- At $t_2 : t_2 = 1 = (b - a)$, $y = z = 2(q)_2$.
- $t_3 : t_3 = 2 = (b - a) = (3 - 1)$, $y = z = 2(q)_3$.

This proportionality is visualized in Fig. 6, where the graph demonstrates the gradient and rational point (C). The position (ijk) corresponds to a dual point at $[t_4 - t_3]$. This dual position is identified as a set of split rings [3], illustrated in Figs. 7 and 6.

Figure 7: Split rings.

Figure 8: Tunneling.

Transformation to Symplectic Groups

We transform the split ring set into a symplectic group[1] using an algorithm derived based on Pascal's triangle (Fig. 8). In this framework:

- One member of the symplectic group is a Lie group ($A = 1$).
- Another member is a Lie-abelian group ($B = 2A$).

This relationship underscores the hierarchical structure and properties of the groups in the algorithm.

Interplay Between Lie Groups and Abelian Varieties

As shown in Fig. 8, the Hodge ring manifests as circles under Ricci flow, superimposed over their equivalent unit squares. Notably:

- At the affine origin, where $X \geq 1$, Lie varieties entangle with Abelian varieties.

Figure 9: Simplex with Pigeonhole Area.

- This phenomenon parallels quantum decoherence [5], illustrating the interplay between these mathematical structures.
- The Lie group acts as the kernel of its associated Abelian group, emphasizing their interconnected order.

The relationship between natural and affine origins is depicted by a simplex in Fig. 9, which highlights the manifold structure.

Rational Points and Continuous Functions

The number of rational points or manifolds is determined by:

$$P = NP = w(2) \cdot r(3) = D = 2(3) = 6,$$

implying:

$$r^3 = C^3 = 3.$$

If $2c = d$, then:

$$\frac{p}{q} = \frac{p}{np} = \frac{3}{6} = \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2n}.$$

Thus, $np = 2n = 2a$ describes a continuous function everywhere in the field, with (a) as the least common factor.

There is a $np = 2n = 2a$ continuous function everywhere in the field with (a) the least common factor. Based on the property of Equation 5, we analyze the following series: 1. For odd integers $2n - 1$:

$2A_n = B_n$			
Equivalent	A_n	B_n	Remark
A	$2x^2$	$2x^2$	$q = p$
B	y^2	y^2	$q = p$
C	$32z^2$	$8z^2$	Trapezoidal parallel sides, $q > p$

Table 1: Table to analyze congruence.

$$\frac{A}{2A} + \frac{3A}{4A} + \frac{5A}{6A} + \frac{7A}{8A} + \dots = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2k-1}{2k},$$

where A is a constant. 2. For even integers $2n$:

$$\frac{A}{2A} + \frac{4A}{8A} + \dots = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k}{2k}.$$

For odd integers $2n-1$, the general term of the series can be expressed as:

$$\frac{2n-1}{2n} = 1 - \frac{1}{2n},$$

which converges to $r = a$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

The series highlights a significant tunneling effect, illustrating the property of (a) to traverse all positions within the global field $\mathbb{Q}$. The function $f(2n)$ appears to bypass classical motion laws, adhering instead to the law of continuity [8]. Such behavior emphasizes the interplay between discrete and continuous systems, converging toward a unified framework of mathematical continuity.

3.1. Tunneling and Congruence Relations

Theorem 5.

$$\begin{aligned} &2A_n = B_n, \quad \text{for odd } n, \quad \text{and} \quad 2C_n = D_n \quad \text{for even } n, \\ &\text{where: } A_n = n = 2x^2 + y^2 + 32z^2, \quad B_n = n = 2x^2 + y^2 + 8z^2, \quad (9) \\ &C_n = n = 8x^2 + 2y^2 + 64z^2, \quad \text{and} \quad D_n = n = 8x^2 + 2y^2 + 16z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 10: The tunneling algorithm.

Analysis for $2A_n = B_n$: Algorithm Derivations

Case 1: Odd n

Consider Table 1 and Figure 10.

Corollary 5.1.

$$\text{Congruence for } 2A_n = B_n. \quad (10)$$

Proof:

If, $B_n = 8$, and $A_n = 4$. then by the tunneling algorithm:

$$n = 3, B = 2A = NP = cq_{n=3} = 2(4) = 8. \quad (11)$$

Therefore, $2A_n = B_n$ for $n = 3$. Consider the algorithm gives $n = 3$. Using Theorem 1:

$$C(Q) \simeq Z^r \oplus C(Q)^{tors} = Z^4 \oplus C(Q_{n=3})^{tors} = Z^4 \oplus C(\sqrt{4})^{tors}, C = 2 \quad (12)$$

Applying cohomology:

$$\begin{aligned} H^p \otimes H^q &\subset H^{2n}(X_1 \times X_2) = H^p \otimes H^q \subset H^{2r}(2 \times 4) \\ &= H^p \otimes H^q \subset H^{12}(Q_{n=3}) = H^p \otimes H^q \subset H^4(8). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Zeta Function Derivation

Using the derived values:

$$\zeta(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{NP + d} = \frac{\pi^2}{(2 \times n) + 2}.$$

For $n = 3$:

$$\zeta(3) = \zeta(C) = \frac{\pi^2}{8}.$$

From the algorithm, join 3 square geometry objects together. Where lines meet, commingled and edges are rational points. These rational points are (14) for $n = 3$. Therefore:

$$3 \equiv 8(\text{mode } np).$$

Case 2: Even n

Corollary 5.2.

$$\text{Congruence for } 2C_n = D_n. \quad (14)$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If, } C_n = 16, \text{ and } D_n = 32. \text{ then by the tunneling algorithm:} \\ n = 6, F = 6A = NP = cq = 2(3). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Consider the algorithm gives $n = 6$. Using Theorem 1:

$$C(Q) \simeq Z^r \oplus C(Q)^{\text{tors}} = Z^6 \oplus C(Q_{n=5})^{\text{tors}} = Z^6 \oplus C(\sqrt{16})^{\text{tors}}, C = 2 \quad (16)$$

Applying cohomology:

$$\begin{aligned} H^p \otimes H^q \subset H^{2n}(X_1 \times X_2) = H^p \otimes H^q \subset H^{2r}(2 \times 16) \\ = H^p \otimes H^q \subset H^{12}(Q_{n=6}) = H^p \otimes H^q \subset H^{12}(32). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Zeta Function Derivation

Using the derived values:

$$\zeta(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{NP + d} = \frac{\pi^2}{(2 \times n) + 2}.$$

For $n = 6$:

$$\zeta(6) = \zeta(F) = \frac{\pi^2}{14}.$$

From the algorithm, we join 6 square geometry objects to get (14) rational points. Therefore:

$$6 \equiv 14(\text{mode } np).$$

$2C_n = D_n$			
Equivalent	C_n	D_n	Remark
A	$8x^2$	$8x^2$	$q = p$
B	$2y^2$	$2y^2$	$q = p$
C	$64z^2$	$16z^2$	Trapezoidal parallel sides, $q > p$

Table 2: Table to analyze congruence.

Case: Rational Points and Areas

For

$$A_n = 2x^2 + y^2 + 32z^2$$

Assume:

$$x^2 = y^2 = z^2 = 1^2 = 1.$$

Substituting into A_n :

$$A_n = 2(1) + 1 + 32(1) = 2 + 1 + 32 = 35.$$

For a truncated cone:

$$p + q = 2x^2 + y^2 = 2n + r.$$

For a cylindrical transformation:

$$p + q = s = 1 + (2i + 1) = 2 + 2i = C(z + r) = C(z + d)$$

where $C = 2$ and $h = z$. If $h \leq r$, we have a Hodge ring.

4. Conclusion

Mathematical structures such as algebraic number theory and theoretical geometry provide a robust framework for addressing profound conjectures like the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture. These structures not only facilitate the development of proofs but also reveal deep connections between seemingly unrelated mathematical domains, unearthing recurring patterns and symmetries.

In this analysis, we explored the Riemann Xi function, defined as:

$$\xi(s) = \frac{1}{2}s(s-1)\pi^{-\frac{s}{2}}\Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right)\zeta(s),$$

where $\Gamma(s)$ is the Gamma function and $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta function. The Xi function encapsulates the symmetry of the critical line $s = \frac{1}{2}$, where all nontrivial zeros of $\zeta(s)$ are conjectured to lie. Symmetry plays a pivotal role in understanding the distribution of these zeros.

To further investigate, we analyzed geometric interpretations of $\zeta(s)$. By defining the area under curves C as A, we found its relationship to symmetries of $\zeta(s)$:

$$A = \frac{1}{2}bh = \frac{1}{2}[s(s-1)]\pi^{\frac{s}{2}},$$

where b and h denote dimensions analogous to square edges. The progression of these areas reflects intrinsic properties of $\zeta(s)$, establishing a correspondence between geometric and analytic constructs. Additionally, we examined numerical sequences and their relationship to the Gamma function. We discussed the series:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{p^n}{n} = 1 + \frac{p^2}{2} + \frac{p^3}{3} + \dots,$$

which exhibits properties analogous to Riemann sums. Its relationship to $\Gamma(s)$ offers insights into the analytic continuation of $\zeta(s)$ and contributes to the ongoing investigation of the Riemann Hypothesis.

Further analysis revealed that symmetry along the critical line relates the progression of zeros and the geometric areas. For example:

$$s = cq + 1 = \frac{1}{2}2 + 1 = 2,$$

where the symmetry is reflected in (2) and (6) along the critical line, as shown in our algorithm (Fig. 10). The relationship between A and B, where $B = 2A$, further highlights the interplay of these constructs:

$$\frac{A}{B} = \frac{1}{2}[s(s-1)]\pi^{\frac{s}{2}} = \frac{\pi}{4} \quad \text{for } s = 2.$$

This leads to:

$$\xi(t) = \frac{1}{2}[s(s-1)]\pi^{\frac{s}{2}}\Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right)\zeta(s).$$

In our graphical analysis (Fig. 6), at the critical line ($x = t = 0$), symmetry simplifies to:

$$r = \frac{1}{2}, \quad \xi(t) = \frac{1}{2}\Gamma.$$

Introducing a normalization factor w , we extend this geometric interpretation:

$$\xi(t) = \frac{d}{2} = \frac{w}{2}\Gamma = bh = wr = 2r = w.$$

This formulation suggests that as Γ progresses from $1 \rightarrow \infty$, the normalization aligns $z = s = p = r = a$ along the critical line. The interplay between $\Gamma(s)$, $\zeta(s)$, and symmetry underscores the pathway for Riemann Hypothesis.

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